

Synthesis of 5-Arylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. Part-II. Oxidative Debenzylation and Cyclisation of 1-Aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides

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Some 5-arylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines have been synthesised by the oxidative debenzoylation and cyclisation of the corresponding 1-aryl substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides.

THE interesting synthesis of 5-arylimino-3-imino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines by the oxidative debenzoylation and cyclisation of 1-aryl-substituted-3-formamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide¹ motivated us to undertake the synthesis of certain 1-aryl-substituted-3-arylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides and to extend this reaction for their facile conversion to 3,5-diarylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. In the present communication, we report the preparation of certain 1-aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (2) and their oxidative debenzoylation and cyclisation to the corresponding 5-arylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (3).

1-Aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamides (1) were prepared by the condensation of *p*-tolylguanidine carbonate with the appropriate arylisothiocyanates^{2,3}. These 3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamides (1) were benzylated with benzyl chloride. The expected 1-aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide free bases (2) so obtained, on oxidation with bromine in chloroform, afforded the related 5-arylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (3). The structure of 3 was finally confirmed as they were also obtained by the direct oxidation of the related 1-aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamides (1). The compounds were further characterised by m.m.p. technique and by identical ir spectra.

The scheme of the reactions can be depicted as

where R = *p*-tolyl, *p*-chlorophenyl, *p*-methoxyphenyl, *p*-ethoxyphenyl, or benzyl; and R' = *p*-tolyl group; bz = C₆H₅CH₂.

Experimental

M. ps. of the compounds were determined by Kofler hot-stage apparatus and are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 720 spectrophotometer.

1-Aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamides (1): A typical example is as follows. *p*-Tolylguanidine carbonate (5 g) and *p*-chlorophenylisothiocyanate (4 ml) were refluxed in ethanol (40 ml) for 1 h. The reaction mixture was filtered and allowed to cool. The expected formamidinothiocarbamide separated was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol, (4 g, 80%), m.p. 158° (base). The results are summarised in Table 1.

1-Aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides (2): The details of a typical experiment are as follows. A mixture of 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamide (5 g), benzyl chloride (2 ml) and ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. On evaporation of the excess solvent and basification, a semi-solid mass was obtained, which on addition of a little ethanol afforded the expected 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide. It was recrystallised from ethanol, (3 g, 60%), m.p. 178°. The results are summarised in Table 2.

In a few cases semi-solid products were obtained, which could not be crystallised. The identity of the compounds 2 was confirmed by their quick reduction to the corresponding 1-aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamides (1) with hydrogen sulphide in ethanolic ammoniacal solution.

5-Arylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines (3): Oxidative debenzoylation and cyclisation of 1-aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamides with bromine in chloroform. The details of a typical experiment are as follows. To 1-

TABLE 1—1-ARYL-SUBSTITUTED-3-*p*-TOLYLFORMAMIDINOTHIOCARBAMIDES*

Reactants**	1-Aryl-substituted-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamides	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
<i>p</i> -Tolylisothiocyanate + T.G.C.	1,3-Di- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide	167	75	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ S
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenylisothiocyanate + T.G.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide	158	80	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ SCl
<i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenylisothiocyanate + T.G.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide	160	70	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ SO
<i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylisothiocyanate + T.G.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide	127	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₄ SO
Benzylisothiocyanate + T.G.C.	1-Benzyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide	Semi-solid	75	—

*Satisfactory analytical data obtained for all compounds. **T.G.C. = *p*-Tolylguanidine carbonate. Typical ir frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 1-*p*-chlorophenyl-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamide: 3 250w (NH stretch, lit.⁴ 3 400 - 3 100), 1 250m (C=S stretch lit.⁴ 1 400 - 1 100), 1 625m cm⁻¹ (-N-C=N, lit.⁴ 1 685 - 1 582).

TABLE 2—1-ARYL-SUBSTITUTED-3-*p*-TOLYLFORMAMIDINO-2-*S*-BENZYLISOTHIOCARBAMIDES*

Reactants**	1-Aryl-substituted-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -benzylisothiocarbamides**	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide + B.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T.H.	180	65	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ S
1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide + B.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T.H.	178	60	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₄ SCl
1- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide + B.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T.H.	Semi-solid	—	—
1- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide + B.C.	1- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T.H.	172	55	C ₂₂ H ₂₄ N ₄ SO
1-Benzyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidinothiocarbamide + B.C.	1-Benzyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -benzyliso-T.H.	Semi-solid	—	—

*Satisfactory elemental data obtained for all compounds. **B.C. = benzyl chloride; T.H. = thlocarbamide.

p-chlorophenyl-3-*p*-tolylformamidino-2-*S*-benzylisothiocarbamide (4 g) moistened with a little chloroform (2 ml), bromine (1 ml) was added in small proportions with vigorous stirring. Debenzylation was evident from the evolution of the lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 30 min at room temperature and washed with ether. Treatment of the resulting mass with ethanol afforded the desired

5-*p*-chlorophenylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1, 2, 4-thiadiazolidine, which was crystallised from ethanol, (58%), m.p. 227°. The results are recorded in Table 3.

The thiadiazolidine bases (3) thus obtained showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with authentic samples obtained by the oxidation of the corresponding 1-aryl-substituted-3-*p*-tolylformamidinothiocarbamides (1). These were further characterised by superimposable ir spectra.

TABLE 3—5-ARYLIMINO-3-*p*-TOLYLIMINO-1,2,4-THIADIAZOLIDINES OXIDATION OF 1-ARYL-SUBSTITUTED-3-*p*-TOLYLFORMAMIDINO-2-*S*-BENZYL ISOTHIOCARBAMIDES*

1-Aryl-substituted-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamido-2- <i>S</i> -benzylisothiocarbamide oxidised**	5-Arylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine formed**	M. p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
1- <i>p</i> -Tolyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -B.T.	5,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-T.D.	205	70	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₄ S
1- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -B.T.	5- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-T.D.	227	58	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₄ SCl
1- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -B.T.	5- <i>p</i> -Ethoxyphenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-T.D.	202	52	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ SO
1- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -B.T.	5- <i>p</i> -Methoxyphenylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-T.D.	190	60	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ SO
1-Benzyl-3- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino-2- <i>S</i> -B.T.	5-Benzylimino-3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-T.D.	270	55	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₄ S

*Satisfactory elemental data obtained for all compounds. **B.T.=benzyl isothiocarbamides; T.D.=1,2,4-thiadiazolidines. Typical ir frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 5-*p*-chlorophenylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidine: 8 275w (NH stretch, lit.⁴ 9 400 - 8 100), 1560m cm⁻¹ (-N=C=N, lit.⁴ 1 685 - 1 582).

Oxidation of 1-aryl-substituted-3-p-tolylformamidothiocarbamides (1) with bromine in ethanol: The formamidinothiocarbamides were dissolved in ethanol and a solution of bromine in dilute ethanol was added till a permanent colour of bromine persisted. After keeping the resulting mass at room temperature for 1 h the expected 5-arylimino-3-*p*-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines precipitated out, which were filtered and crystallised from ethanol and found to be identical with the corresponding compounds mentioned in Table 3.

Reduction of 5-arylimino-3-p-tolylimino-1,2,4-thiadiazolidines by ethanolic ammonical hydrogen sulphide: The thiadiazolidines were dissolved in ethanolic ammonical hydrogen sulphide and a stream of hydrogen sulphide was passed for 3 h. The clear solution on dilution with water or acidification afforded the corresponding formamidinothiocarbamides (1).

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